

Dechlorination and upgrading of waste plastics pyrolysis oil over MWW and TUN zeolites

Alberto Pinto^{a,b}, Lidia Amodio^{a,b}, Martin Kubů^c, Jennifer Cueto^a, Pavla Eliášová^c,
Patricia Pizarro^{a,b}, Jiří Čejka^{c,*}, David P. Serrano^{a,b,**}

^a Thermochemical Processes Unit, IMDEA Energy, Avda. Ramón de la Sagra 3, Móstoles, Madrid 28935, Spain

^b Chemical and Environmental Engineering Group, Rey Juan Carlos University, Móstoles, Madrid, Spain

^c Department of Physical and Macromolecular Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Charles University, Hlavova 8, Prague, Czech Republic

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Waste plastics
MWW
TUN
Aromatics production
Dechlorination
Oil upgrading

ABSTRACT

Pyrolysis is a promising technique for converting waste plastics into oil, but the resulting liquid often contains halogens, particularly chlorine, which pose environmental and corrosion risks when used as fuel or refinery feedstock. These halogens primarily originate from materials such as PVC and other Cl-containing compounds present in the waste. This study evaluates the performance of several zeolites (TNU-9, MCM-22, MCM-49, MCM-56, and MCM-36) in the catalytic dehalogenation and upgrading of a real pyrolysis oil derived from waste plastics with a chlorine content of 290 ppm. Experiments were conducted using a fixed-bed catalytic reactor at 450 °C. All the tested catalysts improved the oil properties, decreasing its paraffin content and favouring the formation of aromatic, cyclic and olefinic hydrocarbons. This is positive regarding the possible use of this oil fraction in the formulation of transportation fuels or as a source of raw chemicals. The deepest modification was observed over MCM-36 zeolite, achieving the highest cracking activity into light olefins (mainly C3 and C4). Its superior performance is attributed to its high external surface area, mesopore volume, and accessible Brønsted acid sites, resulting from its pillar structure. Moreover, MCM-36 was also the zeolite exhibiting the best oil dechlorination capability, which remained relatively stable along the time on stream in contrast to other zeolite catalysts. Analyses of the spent catalysts indicated that the deposited carbonaceous matter accumulates most of the Cl-containing species removed from the oil; hence, the overall oil upgrading process can be considered a combination of catalytic and adsorption effects. This material could be effectively regenerated by a sequential combination of Soxhlet extraction and calcination treatments.

1. Introduction

Global plastic consumption is escalating at an alarming rate of approximately 4 % per year, primarily driven by the excellent properties of plastic materials, such as durability, mechanical strength per unit of weight, versatility in terms of shape, colour, and transparency, as well as low cost and light weight. However, the short lifecycle of many plastic products has led to a substantial increase in plastic waste generation [1]. Despite significant advances in upcycling technologies, recycling rates remain low due to the heterogeneity of plastic waste and contamination with other materials [2]. Waste streams often comprise a mix of polymers such as polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), polystyrene (PS), polyethylene terephthalate (PET), and polyvinyl chloride (PVC), which

may also incorporate a variety of other organic and inorganic additives. The presence of halogenated polymers like PVC and the widespread use of halogenated additives further complicate recycling processes [3]. Given these constraints, feedstock recycling, particularly pyrolysis, has emerged as a promising alternative for the valorisation of mixed waste plastics [4].

Pyrolysis is a relatively simple process that involves the thermal decomposition of organic matter at medium to high temperatures (typically in the range of 400–800 °C) in an inert atmosphere [5]. When applied to plastics, pyrolysis produces several fractions, including oil, gases, waxes, and a solid residue (char). The liquid fraction presents high interest for use as a fuel or as a source of raw chemicals. However, converting this oil into a refined product suitable for industrial

* Corresponding author.

** Corresponding author at: Thermochemical Processes Unit, IMDEA Energy, Avda. Ramón de la Sagra 3, Móstoles, Madrid 28935, Spain.

E-mail addresses: jiri.cejka@natur.cuni.cz (J. Čejka), david.serrano@imdea.org (D.P. Serrano).

applications remains challenging due to its heterogeneous composition, which includes light hydrocarbons (naphtha, gasoline), intermediates (diesel), and heavier fractions (fuel oils, waxes). Moreover, some heteroatoms (N, O, Cl, Br) may also be present depending on the composition of the waste plastics. Thus, chlorinated compounds derived from the PVC and other chlorine-containing species persist in the pyrolysis oil, posing environmental and technical concerns. These include corrosion of refining equipment, pipeline fouling, and the formation of hazardous compounds [6]. Even trace levels of chlorine (<50 ppm) can disqualify the oil for use as fuel or chemical feedstock [7]. Despite these issues, plastic-derived pyrolysis oils possess desirable properties for the production of fuels and/or chemicals [8], whereas their effective utilisation represents a critical step toward a circular economy.

To address these limitations, various upgrading strategies have been investigated, with catalytic processing emerging as one of the most effective approaches [9]. Compared with purely thermal pyrolysis, catalytic upgrading not only improves oil quality by removing undesired heteroatoms but also tailors the composition towards light hydrocarbons and aromatics [10]. Catalysts can be employed either directly during pyrolysis [11–15] or as a post-treatment of the liquid phase, although the latter has been little investigated in the literature using oils derived from real waste plastics. In this way, Lee et al. [16] upgraded pyrolysis wax oil from municipal plastic waste using HZSM-5, HY, and mordenite (HM). HZSM-5 yielded a high share of gas (51.0 wt%) and promoted the formation of aromatics in the liquid phase, HY zeolite provided a higher paraffin content (C_5 – C_6), while HM showed the lowest activity due to its 1D pore structure. Wang et al. [17] combined distillation and catalytic cracking with zeolite 4A, a commercial Cu-based catalyst manufactured by Clariant Co (MDC-7), and Ni-based catalysts in the upgrading of plastic oil from Korea. Ni maximised diesel-like fractions (66.3 wt%) and deoxygenation, while MDC-7 enhanced gasoline-like fractions (15.8 wt%) with aromatic and naphthenic character. Both studies illustrate the effectiveness of zeolites, whose adjustable acidity, shape-selective properties, and thermal stability make them suitable for cracking, aromatisation, and dehalogenation reactions [18,19]. Moreover, in the case of plastic pyrolysis oils, zeolite accessibility to bulky molecules remains a critical challenge that can restrict catalytic efficiency, since many of the components present are bulky species [20]. On the other hand, these works did not address the issue of halogens contained in the oil phase.

Zeolites can crystallise as three-dimensional structures (3D) as well as two-dimensional ones (2D), where growth is restricted to one direction. The area of 2D zeolites has been expanding rapidly with novel discoveries and insights, such as the discovery of MCM-22P, a zeolite layered precursor of the zeolite MCM-22 (from MWW family) [21]. The MWW framework consists of a two-dimensional channel system with 10-ring sinusoidal channels (0.41×0.51 nm) running within the layers and large 12-ring supercages (1.82 nm in diameter) interconnected through 6-ring windows. These supercages are accessible from the external surface through 10-ring openings, but they do not form a continuous channel system. Consequently, MCM-22, MCM-49, MCM-56 and MCM-36, and others, have been identified, each differing in the stacking arrangement of MCM-22 monolayers [22,23] (Scheme 1). The layered precursor MCM-22P exhibits vertically aligned layers with an interlayer separation of 2.7 nm, which is 0.2 nm greater than the fully developed 3D framework (2.5 nm) obtained upon calcination of MCM-22P. Zeolite MCM-49 is synthesised directly as a 3D MWW structure with connectivity identical to the calcined form of MCM-22 (2.5 nm). The main difference between MCM-22 and MCM-49 zeolites is their chemical composition, with MCM-49 having higher aluminium content. Meanwhile, zeolite MCM-56 represents a delaminated MWW structure where the MWW layers are in a house-of-cards arrangement (see Scheme 1). Interestingly, MCM-56 zeolite serves as an intermediate in the hydrothermal synthesis of MCM-49 [22]. The layered structure of MCM-22P can be further utilised to form additional pores through swelling and pillaring processes, leading to the preparation of micro-mesoporous zeolite MCM-36 (see Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Structural relationship between the MWW zeolite family.

On the other hand, zeolite TNU-9 (with IZA code TUN) is to some extent structurally similar to MWW zeolite. It directly crystallises as a 3D zeolite. Its structural projection along the y-axis bears resemblance to ZSM-5 or ZSM-11, albeit with distinctly different interlayer connections. The framework features two distinct types of straight 10-ring channels aligned parallel to the y-axis, with dimensions of 0.52×0.60 nm and 0.51×0.55 nm. Additionally, channels oriented perpendicular to the y-axis interconnect these straight channels, giving rise to a three-dimensional 10-ring channel system [24]. The range of molar Si/Al ratios of this material can be similar to that of MWW zeolites. Thus, the main difference between 3D MWW zeolites like MCM-22 and MCM-49, and TNU-9 lies in their pore dimensionality – MWW has 2D channels, while TNU-9 has a 3D channel system. Despite this difference, both MWW and TNU-9 feature similar 10-ring channel dimensions. However, MWW-type zeolites additionally contain 12-ring side pockets.

In this context, the present study investigates the use of zeolites as catalysts to enhance the quality of pyrolysis oils derived from mixed plastic waste. Specifically, using a real plastics pyrolysis oil as feedstock, the work is focused on the effect of using different zeolite structures – TNU-9, MCM-22, MCM-49, MCM-56, and MCM-36 – on two critical issues related to the upgrading of this fraction: the removal of halogenated contaminants and the formation of aromatic hydrocarbons. In this way, it should be highlighted that the feedstock here employed is not coming from the pyrolysis of a model plastic mixture, but it has been generated at an industrial scale by pyrolysis of real waste plastics, thus facing the challenges associated with the practical application of this kind of processes.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Synthesis of MWW and TUN zeolites

The synthesis of MCM-22P/MCM-22, MCM-49, MCM-56, and MCM-36 was carried out according to the literature [25] with some minor modifications. For the preparation of MWW materials hexamethylenimine (HMI) was used as a structure-directing agent (SDA).

Layered precursor MCM-22P was synthesised hydrothermally from the synthetic gel with Si/Al molar ratio equal to 40. The synthesis gel was prepared by mixing 400 H₂O and 12.2 g of 50 wt% NaOH solution. 2.79 g of NaAlO₂ (53 % Al₂O₃, 42,5 % Na₂O) was added to the basic solution, which was then stirred until dissolved. Subsequently, 232.4 g of LUDOX AS30 solution was added. The gel was stirred for 10 min. Finally, 38.34 g of HMI was added and the mixture was stirred for the

next 10 min. The crystallisation was performed in 1-litre Paar autoclave with inner stirring at 143 °C for 5 days. The solid product was filtered, washed out with distilled water and dried at 65 °C.

MCM-49 and MCM-56 zeolites were synthesised from the same reaction gel under the same conditions (with Si/Al molar ratio of the gel equal to 13). Their synthesis differs in the crystallisation time and silica source. The synthesis gel was prepared by mixing 396 g of H₂O and 9 g of 50 wt% NaOH solution. 9.75 g of NaAlO₂ (53 % Al₂O₃, 42,5 % Na₂O) was added to the basic solution, which was then stirred until dissolved. Subsequently, the solution was poured into an autoclave with 77.1 g of SiO₂ (Ultrasil VN5). The gel was stirred for 10 min. Finally, 40.8 g of HMI was added and the mixture was stirred for the next 10 min. The crystallisation was performed in 1-litre Paar autoclave with inner stirring at 145 °C. The synthesis was stopped after exactly 32.5 h in the case of MCM-56 zeolite and after 216 h in the case of MCM-49 zeolite. The solid product was filtered off, washed out with distilled water and dried at 65 °C.

Pillared MCM-36 was prepared from layered MCM-22P. The layered MCM-22P was synthesised with the same procedure described above, but using a different Si/Al molar ratio of the gel (SiAl = 15). The procedure was as follows: 1 g of MCM-22P was stirred in a solution of hexadecyltrimethylammonium chloride (25 wt%, 27 g) and tetrapropylammonium hydroxide (40 wt%, 3 g) for 20 h. The solid was then separated by centrifugation for 20 min at 4000 RPM speed and repeatedly washed with ethanol followed by centrifugation. The so-called swollen MCM-22P, labelled as MCM-22SW, was then stirred with tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) solution (with a ratio of 1 g of solid to 15 ml of TEOS) for 24 h at 85 °C. The solid was separated by centrifugation (20 min, 4000 RPM), washed with ethanol followed by centrifugation and finally dried at 65 °C.

The calcination of all MWW samples was performed in two steps: first heating to 482 °C with temperature ramp of 3 °C/min under a nitrogen atmosphere, maintaining this temperature constant for 3 h, then switching to air atmosphere and increasing the temperature up to 540 °C with a ramp of 2 °C/min and calcination for 6 h.

TNU-9 (TUN) zeolite was synthesised according to the reference [25] with a minor modification in the aluminium source. The organic SDA cation 1,4-bis(N-methylpyrrolidinium) butane (1,4-MPB) was prepared according to the literature [26]. The synthesis gel was prepared by mixing 600 g of H₂O and 48.2 g of SDA. Then, 24.8 g of solid NaOH was added to the mixture was stirred until dissolved. 10.4 g of Al (NO₃)₃·9H₂O was added and stirred until dissolved. Subsequently, the solution was poured into an autoclave with 52.6 g of SiO₂ (Cab-O-Sil M5). The gel was stirred for 20 min. The crystallisation was performed in a 1-litre Paar autoclave with inner stirring at 160 °C for 12 days. The solid product was filtered, washed out with distilled water and dried at 65 °C. The as-synthesised zeolite was calcined at 560 °C with a ramp of 1 °C/min for 12 h.

All calcined zeolites were converted to NH₄⁺ form by four times repeated ion-exchange with 0.5 M NH₄NO₃ solution (1 g/100 ml solution). Prior to the catalytic test, the NH₄⁺-forms of zeolites were activated by heating to 450 °C with a ramp of 10 °C/min for 4 h to obtain the H⁺-form of zeolites.

2.2. Characterisation of prepared zeolites

Powder XRD patterns were collected on a Bruker AXS D8 Advance diffractometer equipped with a DLYNXYE XE-T detector in Bragg–Brentano geometry using Cu K α (λ = 1.54056 Å) radiation operated at 30 mA and 40 kV. Data were collected in continuous mode over a 2 θ range of 3–40° or 1–40° in the case of MCM-36.

Nitrogen sorption measurements were performed at –196 °C on a static volumetric 3Flex (Micromeritics) apparatus. Before measurement, the samples were outgassed at 300 °C for 8 h with a turbo molecular pump at $p < 1$ Pa. The BET method was applied to calculate the specific surface area in the relative pressure range (p/p_0) of 0.05 – 0.20. The

micropore volume (V_{micro}) and the external surface (S_{ext}) were evaluated using the *t*-plot method. The adsorbed amount at $p/p_0 = 0.95$ reflects the total pore volume (V_{total}).

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) measurements were carried out on JEOL JSM-6380 LV and JEOL JSM-IT800 microscopes to investigate the morphology of the crystals. All samples were deposited on conductive carbon tape mounted onto the SEM holder.

Elemental analysis was performed by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS; Agilent 7900 ICP-MS). A closed vessel containing a mixture of 50 mg of zeolite, 1.8 ml of HF, 5.4 ml of HCl, and 1.8 ml of HNO₃ was placed in a microwave oven to dissolve the zeolite. To complex the surplus HF after cooling down, 13.5 ml of H₃BO₃ was added and reheated in the microwave oven.

The acid properties of the zeolites were investigated by Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy of adsorbed pyridine (FTIR-Py) and 2,6-di-tert-butylpyridine (FTIR-DTBP). For this purpose, the zeolites were pressed into self-supporting wafers with a density of approximately 10 mg·cm⁻² and activated *in situ* at 450 °C and $p = 5.10^{-5}$ Torr for 4 h. FTIR spectra were recorded using a Nicolet iS50 spectrometer with a transmission MCT/B detector with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ by collecting 128 scans for a single spectrum at room temperature. Pyridine sorption was performed for 20 min at 150, 250, 350 and 450 °C, followed by 20-min desorption at the same temperature. The number of Brønsted acid sites (BAS) was estimated based on the integral intensity of the band at 1545 cm⁻¹. The molar absorption coefficient used in the case of MWW zeolites was 0.044 cm²· μmol^{-1} , commonly used for MWW zeolites [26, 27]. The number of Lewis acid sites (LAS) was estimated from the integral intensities of the bands at 1454 cm⁻¹ using the molar absorption coefficient of 0.165 cm²· μmol^{-1} [26,27]. In the case of zeolite TNU-9 (TUN), the number of BAS and LAS sites was estimated using molar absorption coefficients of 1.67 and 2.22 cm²· μmol^{-1} , respectively [28]. A larger probe molecule, 2,6-di-tert-butylpyridine (DTBP) with a kinetic diameter of 0.79 nm, was used to determine the ‘accessibility’ of acid sites within prepared zeolites [29,30]. DTBP adsorption took place at 150 °C at equilibrium probe vapour pressure for 15 min. Desorption proceeded at the same temperature for 1 h, followed by the collection of spectra at room temperature. Molar absorption coefficient used for the evaluation of BAS accessible for DTBP was 5.22 cm²· μmol^{-1} using the integral intensity of the absorption band at ca. 3360 cm⁻¹ [31].

2.3. Feedstock characterisation

The feedstock used in this work is a plastic pyrolysis oil provided by Repsol (Spain). Several analytical techniques were used to characterise it, as described below.

The elemental composition (CHNS-O) was determined in a Thermo Scientific FLASH 2000 CHNS/O micro-elemental analyser. The chlorine concentration was measured using an active oxidative decomposition technique (AOD) with a bomb calorimeter (IKA) according to EPA 5050 and EPA 9056 A standards. The resulting solution was analysed by ion chromatography (IC) with a Metrohm IC 930 Compact IC Flex chromatograph equipped with a Metrosep A Supp 7–150/4.0 column and A Supp 5 Guard/4.0 as pre-column. A Multi Element Anion Standard of 25 ppm (F⁻, Cl⁻, Br⁻, NO₂⁻, NO₃⁻, PO₄³⁻, SO₄²⁻) by Reagecon was employed to calibrate.

The oil molecular composition was determined by gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (GC-MS) using an Agilent 7820 A GC system connected to a 5977B MSD detector, and equipped with a fused silica HP5-MS UI column (30 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 mm). A Template NIST spectral library was employed for the identification of compounds, just those having a minimum matching factor of 80/100 being considered. The feed sample was diluted to a mass ratio of 1:20 in a solution of 1000 ppm of cyclohexanol (internal standard) in dioxane. After defining the main product families, which are mono-aromatic hydrocarbons (MAH), poly-aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH), indanes (IND), paraffins (PAR), olefins (OL) and naphthenes (NAPH), the major

compounds of the different families were calibrated. This method was described in previous works and was used to estimate the mass concentration of the principal families [32,33]. Calibration was applied to all compounds with a relative area greater than 10 % of the internal standard area.

2.4. Catalytic oil upgrading tests

Catalytic upgrading experiments of the raw oil were performed in a continuous-flow fixed bed reactor (3/4" i.d. and 26 cm length) at 450 °C, this temperature being selected based on previous results obtained working within the 400–450 °C range [14,19]. Temperature monitoring inside the reactor was carried out using a K-thermocouple. Two weight hourly space velocities (WHSV) of 5 and 10 h⁻¹ were tested. Figure 1 shows a scheme of the reaction system used and described below.

Prior to initiating the reaction, the entire system was purged with nitrogen to eliminate residual oxygen and moisture. The reactor temperature was then gradually increased to 450 °C under a continuous nitrogen flow. Once the target temperature was reached, the pyrolysis oil feed was introduced into the reactor at a controlled rate of 5 g/h using a syringe pump and maintained for 4 h.

Throughout the experiment, a nitrogen (N₂) sweep gas was continuously supplied at a flow rate of 50 ml/min, regulated by a mass flow controller (Bronkhorst, El-Flow), and maintained under atmospheric pressure. This inert carrier gas facilitated the transport of vapours and minimised secondary reactions.

The oil feed was directed into the catalytic bed to come into contact with the selected zeolite catalysts (MCM-22, MCM-49, MCM-56, MCM-36 and TNU-9). Each catalyst was pelletized and sieved to achieve a uniform particle size distribution ranging from 0.18 to 0.25 mm. The catalyst was carefully positioned at the centre of the catalytic zone using a stainless-steel support system, comprising metallic nets and quartz wool, to ensure a stable bed height and optimal contact between the oil vapours and the catalytic surface.

At the bottom of the reactor, a liquid condensation system cooled by an ice bath was installed to collect condensable products. In these experiments, the oil was collected every hour and was analysed by AOD/

IC, CHNS/O and GC-MS, in a similar way as described in section 2.3 for the raw oil characterisation. The results were expressed with respect to the average times on stream (TOS) of 0.5, 1.5, 2.5, and 3.5 h. Additionally, for GC-MS analysis of the liquid products, it was necessary to dilute the samples in cyclohexanol-dioxane solution (1:200) to avoid saturation of major peaks. Two bubblers containing a Na₂CO₃ solution (0.1 M), immersed in a water-ice bath (0 °C), were used to trap the HCl eventually produced during the reactions. These bubblers were changed every hour, and the recovered solutions were analysed by IC.

A continuous gas flow meter was used for the gas quantification at the exit of the condensation system, collecting a gas sampling bag every 30 min. After that, the gas composition was determined by a μ-GC (Agilent Technologies, 490) equipped with a molecular sieve (Molsieve 5 Å), PPQ and 5CB columns and three thermal conductivity detectors (TCD). Helium was used as the carrier gas. The calibrated gaseous components, which were quantified, included N₂, H₂, CO, CO₂, CH₄, C₂H₄, C₂H₆, C₃H₆, C₃H₈, C₄H₈ and C₄H₁₀.

The mass balance was closed by quantifying the weight of the different fractions derived from the upgrading process (oil and gas), whereas the coke content in the spent catalyst was determined by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) using a NETZSCH 449 thermobalance equipped with a SiC furnace. The analysis was performed under an air atmosphere (100 Nml/min), with a heating rate of 10 °C/min up to 900 °C, followed by an isothermal step at 900 °C for 30 min. The hourly coke yield was estimated from the total weight of coke collected after the experiments, divided by the total reaction time, as it was not possible to collect hourly samples of this fraction. The mass balances were closed at a minimum of 95 wt% in all the experiments. To close the chlorine balance, the amount of this element retained in the catalyst after the reaction was measured. For this purpose, a Soxhlet extraction of the spent catalyst (0.3 g) was carried out for 4 h using 100 ml of tetrahydrofuran (THF). The chlorine content in the THF solution was analysed by AOD/IC.

The spent catalyst was regenerated by Soxhlet extraction in THF under identical conditions to those described above for complete chlorine removal. The recovered solid was subsequently calcined in static air at 550 °C, with a heating rate of 1.8 °C min⁻¹ and a dwell time of 5 h, to eliminate any carbonaceous deposits (coke) still remaining in the

Fig. 1. Experimental set-up used in the catalytic tests of waste plastics pyrolysis oil upgrading.

catalyst. The regenerated catalyst was then evaluated again for the upgrading of the waste plastics pyrolysis oil ($T = 450\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\text{WHSV} = 10\text{ h}^{-1}$).

Reproducibility of the pyrolysis oil upgrading tests, as well as of the subsequent products analyses, was assessed by performing two replicas, hence determining the average error in terms of error bars (data shown in figures).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Physicochemical properties of zeolite samples

Synthesised zeolites from the MWW family differ in the spatial arrangement of the layers and chemical composition, as has been commented in the introduction section and displayed in Scheme 1. Both MCM-22 and MCM-49 zeolites have a three-dimensional character, MCM-49 being the aluminium-richer counterpart to MCM-22 (with Si/Al molar ratio 10.4 vs 31.2).

The synthetic gel for MCM-49 and MCM-56 had the same chemical composition (with Si/Al molar ratio = 13). First, randomly assembled layers with MWW topology are formed (after 32.5 h). The layers' arrangement is often visualised as house-of-cards and the product is designated as MCM-56 (see Scheme 1). In the XRD pattern, MCM-56 exhibits a typical broad band between 8 and $10^{\circ} 2\theta$ (Figure 2), indicating the vertical misalignment of the layers [21]. When the synthesis time is prolonged (up to 216 h), the layers are arranged and condensed into the three-dimensional structure of MCM-49. The peaks (101) at $8^{\circ} 2\theta$ and (102) at $10^{\circ} 2\theta$ become then clearly separated, evidencing the 3D order alignment. In the SEM images (Figure 3), MCM-56 showed agglomerates with sizes larger than $5\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ consisting of intergrown plate-like crystals. The individual crystallites present dimensions smaller than $0.5\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ and their agglomerates resemble cauliflower-type structures. In contrast, for MCM-49, the size of plate-shape crystallites is larger than $1\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ but they also form aggregates of similar sizes as MCM-56.

Zeolite MCM-22 is formed via its layered precursor MCM-22P (Scheme 1). After calcination, MCM-22 exhibits an XRD powder diffraction pattern similar to MCM-49 but with higher intensities (Figure 2). Very small intensity peaks at 7.4 , 7.6 , 8.9 and $21^{\circ} 2\theta$ indicate the minor presence (less than 5 %) of an impurity phase, probably of MTW topology. The SEM images of MCM-22 show agglomerates of similar size to those of MCM-56 and individual crystallites around $1\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ (Figure 3).

In order to introduce additional mesoporosity, the layered MCM-22P was swollen with long-chain organic surfactants. These organic molecules increased the interlayer space enough to subsequently enable the

formation of more thermally stable inorganic SiO_2 pillars (more details are provided in the Experimental part). The so-prepared material is called MCM-36 (see Scheme 1), and in the XRD pattern, the first interlayer peak appears at $1.85^{\circ} 2\theta$ corresponding to 4.8 nm . Considering the approximate thickness of MWW layers to be 2.5 nm [21], the interlayer distance is about 2.3 nm . The pillaring treatment dilutes the amount of acid sites per weight of the final material due to the addition of SiO_2 species. The calcined MCM-36 has Si/Al molar ratio determined as 23.8 according to ICP-MS. From SEM images, the presence of agglomerates in this material is similar to that of MCM-56 (Figure 3). The synthesised TNU-9 sample is, according to its XRD pattern, a well-crystalline zeolite with Si/Al molar ratio of 29.5 (determined by ICP-MS). TNU-9 is formed by elongated and relatively large crystals with rectangular facets and sizes of several microns (Figure 3).

The nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms confirmed the purely microporous nature of TNU-9 showing a typical type I isotherm with a BET surface area of $524\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$, total pore volume of $0.21\text{ cm}^3\text{ g}^{-1}$ and micropore volume of $0.19\text{ cm}^3\text{ g}^{-1}$ (Figure 2). Isotherms of MCM-22 and MCM-49 have the same shape of type I, although with a more pronounced slope at intermediate pressures, which is indicative of the contribution of the external surface. Thus, both zeolites have almost double the external surface areas compared to the TNU-9 zeolite (see Table 1). Likewise, the small hysteresis loop observed in these samples at high relative pressures (starting above $p/p_0 = 0.6$) is typical for interparticle voids and particle aggregates [34]. This finding is a result of plate-like crystallite aggregates, as observed in SEM images (Figure 3). Micropore volumes of 0.19 and $0.16\text{ cm}^3\text{ g}^{-1}$ account for around 61 % and 55 % of the total pore volumes in MCM-22 and MCM-49, respectively. On the other hand, the house-of-cards layer arrangement in MCM-56 causes significant pronouncement of the hysteresis loop, which can be classified as type H4 according to IUPAC classification [34], being associated with the interparticle voids between the layers. The external surface area of $127\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$ in MCM-56 is almost double that of MCM-22 and MCM-49 (Table 1). The micropore volume of MCM-56 ($0.12\text{ cm}^3\text{ g}^{-1}$) represents only 25 % of the total pore volume, denoting a great contribution of the interparticle porosity in this sample. Finally, the pillared MCM-36 reveals a distinct isotherm profile compared to the other MWW family members. In addition to the adsorption at low relative pressures ($p/p_0 < 0.01$), the N_2 uptake sharply increases in the region $p/p_0 0.01\text{--}0.3$, which is typical for a broader distribution of pores below 4 nm [35]. From the BET surface area of $728\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$, $486\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$ is assigned to the external surface and the micropore volume of $0.10\text{ cm}^3\text{ g}^{-1}$ represents only a small portion of the total pore volume of $0.45\text{ cm}^3\text{ g}^{-1}$. These data denote the great contribution of mesopores in MCM-36 as a consequence of the pillaring treatment.

FTIR study using pyridine as a probe molecule was performed to

Fig. 2. XRD powder patterns of synthesised zeolites of MWW family and TUN (on left) and their N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherms measured at 77 K (on right).

Fig. 3. SEM images of MWW and TUN zeolites and schemes of their framework with pore size dimensions.

Table 1

Textural and acidic properties of MWW and TUN zeolites determined by N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms at 77 K and FTIR study using pyridine (PYR) and 2,6-di-tert-butylpyridine (DTBPy) as probe molecules and chemical composition analysed by ICP-MS. The amounts of Brønsted and Lewis sites were determined by PYR and DTBPy adsorbed at 150 °C (more details in experimental part).

Zeolite	Si/Al (ICP)	Textural properties (from N ₂ sorption)				Amount of acid sites		
		BET (m ² g ⁻¹)	S _{ext} (m ² g ⁻¹)	V _{total} (cm ³ g ⁻¹)	V _{micro} (cm ³ g ⁻¹)	FTIR-PYR		FTIR-DTBPY
						Brønsted (mmol/g)	Lewis (mmol/g)	Brønsted (mmol/g)
TNU-9	29.5	524	31	0.21	0.19	0.34	0.12	< 0.01
MCM-22	31.2	541	68	0.31	0.19	0.39	0.07	0.04
MCM-49	10.4	460	66	0.29	0.16	0.91	0.22	0.06
MCM-56	9.3	406	127	0.48	0.12	0.73	0.22	0.08
MCM-36	23.8	728	486	0.45	0.10	0.36	0.09	0.15

quantify Brønsted and Lewis acid sites in the prepared zeolites. Figure S1 shows the spectra of all zeolites investigated in the region of hydroxyl vibrations (A) and in the region of pyridine vibrations (B). The absorption band between 3745 and 3747 cm⁻¹ present in all zeolites is assigned to terminal silanol groups. This band is the most pronounced in MCM-36, which contains additional SiO₂-pillars between the MWW layers. In the spectra of TNU-9, MCM-56 and MCM-49 there is a relatively weak absorption band at 3665–3670 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of extra-framework aluminium species. The band at 3614 cm⁻¹ in TNU-9 and in the range 3620–3622 cm⁻¹ in MWW zeolites is attributed to bridging acidic Si-(OH)-Al groups – the Brønsted sites. After pyridine adsorption, this band completely disappears in all samples demonstrating good accessibility of pyridine molecules to all Brønsted sites. In the region of pyridine vibrations typical bands of pyridine interacting with Brønsted and Lewis acid sites appeared. Absorption band around 1545 cm⁻¹ is characteristic for pyridine interacting with Brønsted acid sites while band around 1455 cm⁻¹ is attributed to pyridine being in interaction with Lewis acid sites. The less intensive band at 1442 cm⁻¹ in TNU-9 and at 1446–1447 cm⁻¹ in all MWW samples is connected with the pyridine interaction with silanol groups via weak van der Waals bonds. These bands vanish with increasing temperature of desorption. At 350 °C these bands are not visible in all MWW samples (or only negligible) but still well recognized in TNU-9 zeolite. With the increasing desorption temperature, the intensity of 1545 cm⁻¹ band, associated with Brønsted acid sites, is decreasing but even at 450 °C the band is still visible in all MWW zeolites, while it almost completely vanished in TNU-9. Comparing the concentrations of Brønsted sites determined at 150 and 350 °C, the percentage of sites preserved at the higher temperature follow this order: MCM-22 (87 %) > MCM-36 (81 %) > MCM-49 (70 %) > MCM-56 (62 %) > TUN-9 (56 %) (for details see Supporting Information Table 1). We can assume on the presence of the strongest Brønsted sites in the well-crystalline three-dimensional framework of MCM-22 and MCM-36. On the other hand, the weakest Brønsted sites are present in zeolite TNU-9.

Additionally, 2,6-di-tert-butylpyridine (DTBPy) molecule was used as a probe molecule to determine the Brønsted acid sites located on the external surface of zeolites since DTBPy, with a kinetic diameter of 0.79 nm, is too bulky to enter 10-ring channels of MWW and TUN zeolites [29]. The highest concentration of such sites was found with zeolites having two-dimensional layers arrangement and largest external surface area. The concentration of Brønsted sites on the external surface decreases in the following order, closely following the same order of decreasing external surface area: MCM-36 (0.15 mmol.g⁻¹, 486 m²g⁻¹) > MCM-56 (0.08 mmol.g⁻¹, 127 m²g⁻¹) > MCM-49 (0.06 mmol.g⁻¹, 66 m²g⁻¹) > MCM-22 (0.04 mmol/g, 68 m²g⁻¹) > TNU-9 (< 0.01 mmol.g⁻¹, 31 m²g⁻¹).

3.2. Raw oil characterisation

The raw oil obtained from plastic waste thermal pyrolysis was thoroughly characterised to assess its suitability for catalytic upgrading. Elemental analysis revealed a highly carbonaceous matrix, with

85.52 wt% carbon, 14.45 wt% hydrogen, and a significant chlorine content of 0.029 wt% (290 ppm)—a key factor due to its potential to corrode downstream equipment if the oil is to be processed in refinery units. Attempts to identify the Cl-containing species by GC-MS failed, probably because of the presence of a broad variety of organochloride components at very low concentrations. In this way, it must be taken into account that, as above indicated, this feedstock is not coming from the pyrolysis of a model plastic mixture but it has been generated at industrial scale by pyrolysis of real waste plastics, so the presence of many chlorinated precursors in the raw waste materials, which are transformed into a broad range of halogenated species during the thermal decomposition process, can be expected. Thus, it is well-known that in the case of the pyrolysis of PVC-containing streams, there is first a release of HCl, which subsequently reacts with organic components forming different organochlorides species [19,36].

The molecular composition and carbon number distribution are summarised in Figure 4, offering a comprehensive view of the oil's complexity and highlighting key challenges for catalytic processing. As it can be observed, the oil is predominantly composed of aliphatic hydrocarbons, including paraffins (35.8 wt%), olefins (8.2 wt%), and naphthenes (7.2 wt%), along with a minor fraction of monoaromatics (5.5 wt%). Notably, a substantial proportion (43.2 wt%) corresponds mostly to compounds that cannot be detected in the GC-MS analyses (they are calculated by difference after applying the calibration to the identified components). These compounds likely include heavier hydrocarbons with more than 30 carbon atoms, as supported by the long-tailed profile observed in the carbon number distribution. This distribution spans from C7 to beyond C30 and suggests the presence of structurally complex and oligomeric species formed during thermal degradation. The significant abundance of high-molecular-weight species underscores the necessity of using catalysts with high accessibility to active sites for the oil upgrading treatments.

3.3. Zeolite performance in the upgrading of waste plastics pyrolysis oil

The catalytic performance of the five distinct zeolites (MCM-22, MCM-49, MCM-56, MCM-36, and TNU-9) was evaluated for the upgrading of the real waste plastics pyrolysis oil at 450 °C using a weight hourly space velocity (WHSV) of 5 h⁻¹. The key performance metrics, including product distributions and compositional changes, have been assessed and correlated with the structural and acidic properties thoroughly discussed in Section 3.1 and summarised in Table 1.

Figure 5A shows the distribution of product yields (oil, gas, and coke) obtained with each zeolite, together with a blank experiment carried out in the absence of a catalyst. The blank run resulted in almost complete recovery of the feed as liquid (≈100 wt%), with negligible gas formation. This result confirms that, without zeolite catalysts, the oil remains largely untransformed. In contrast, all the zeolites tested (TNU-9, MCM-22, MCM-49, MCM-56, and MCM-36) markedly decreased the oil fraction yield, while promoting the formation of gaseous products and, to a lesser extent, of coke.

TNU-9 delivered the lowest gas yield that can be attributed to its

Fig. 4. Composition of the waste plastics pyrolysis oil obtained by GC-MS as a function of the (A) main families detected and (B) number of carbon atoms.

relatively low external surface area ($31 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$) and high Si/Al ratio (29.5). These features minimise the extension of cracking reactions [37]. Thus, although TNU-9 possesses a moderate Brønsted acid site density ($0.34 \text{ mmol} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$ as measured by FTIR-PYR), the absence of acid sites accessible on the external surface (confirmed by FTIR-DTBPY) limits the cracking of large components, contributing to the small gas production observed with this catalyst.

MCM-22 and MCM-49 zeolites both demonstrated relatively high oil yields, reaching 86 and 88 wt%, respectively. While these zeolites differ significantly in terms of their Si/Al ratios (31.2 for MCM-22 vs. 10.4 for MCM-49) and total Brønsted acidity (0.39 vs. 0.91 mmol/g , respectively), their overall performance remains comparable. This similarity can be explained by their closely matched external surface areas ($68 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$ for MCM-22 and $66 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$ for MCM-49) and nearly equivalent accessible Brønsted acid sites, as measured by FTIR-DTBPY (0.04 and

0.06 mmol/g , respectively). The external surface area and accessible acidity turned out to be critical parameters in determining catalytic effectiveness in upgrading reactions due to the large molecular size of many of the components present in the raw oil as described in section 3.2. However, the gas composition differs markedly between these two materials, particularly regarding C_3H_8 and C_4H_8 components when MCM-49 exhibits higher selectivity towards propane (C_3H_8), while MCM-22 favours the formation of butene (C_4H_8), indicating distinct cracking and hydrogen transfer behaviours between the two zeolites. It probably arises from their quite different Al content, the distinct concentration of acid sites as well as their different strength (see Supporting information, Table S1).

On the other hand, MCM-56 and MCM-36 exhibit lower oil yields (79 and 73 wt%, respectively) and higher gas formation, denoting they are more active materials for cracking reactions. This can be attributed to

Fig. 5. Overall yields obtained in the plastic pyrolysis oil upgrading using different zeolites ($T = 450^\circ \text{C}$, $\text{WHSV} = 5 \text{ h}^{-1}$, $t = 0 - 4 \text{ h}$): (A) product fractions (oil, gas and coke), and (B) individual hydrocarbons identified in the gaseous fraction.

the relatively high accessible concentration of Brønsted acid sites (0.08 and 0.13 mmol·g⁻¹, respectively). These characteristics enhance the cracking of pyrolytic vapours into lighter compounds, increasing gas yields. In Figure 5B, the enhanced gas formation is evidenced by the significantly higher yields of C₃+ aliphatic hydrocarbons. MCM-36, in particular, shows outstanding selectivity towards C₃-C₄ olefins, producing about 7 wt% of propene (C₃H₆) and around 10.6 wt% of butenes (C₄H₈). MCM-56 follows closely with about 6.4 wt% C₃H₆ and 3.4 wt% C₄H₈, reflecting similar catalytic behaviour. These elevated olefin yields highlight the efficiency of both zeolite catalysts in facilitating β-scission reactions. In addition to olefins, both catalysts also generate, to a minor extent, notable amounts of light paraffins, such as propane (C₃H₈) and butane (C₄H₁₀). These saturated hydrocarbons are most likely formed through the cracking of heavier paraffinic chains and hydrogen-transfer reactions. All these findings indicate a high degree of catalytic activity of MCM-36 and MCM-56, consistent with their enhanced accessibility and acidic properties.

Some reasonable differences in coke production are observed among the tested materials. Zeolites with higher cracking activity and greater external surface area, such as MCM-56 and MCM-36, show relatively higher coke formation, reaching coke yields of about 2.1 and 2.7 wt%, respectively. In contrast, zeolite TNU-9 exhibited significantly lower coke production, just 0.7 wt% yield, indicating a lower tendency for the formation of carbonaceous deposits under the same conditions. Accordingly, the deposition of carbonaceous matter seems to be also enhanced for the zeolite samples showing large external surface areas. These results are consistent with the findings of Tarach et al. [38], who reported a higher coke formation on hierarchical ZSM-5 zeolites compared to microcrystalline ZSM-5 during polyethylene cracking.

The molecular composition of the oils obtained from catalytic pyrolysis was characterised using gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC-MS). The results, grouped by hydrocarbon families, are shown in Figure 6, providing insights into the chemical quality and conversion pathways of the upgraded oils. As it is observed, the blank experiment has a distribution similar to the original oil feed. This indicates that, without the catalyst, the molecular composition in the feedstock remains largely unchanged. Importantly, the presence of zeolite catalysts also reduced the fraction of heavy compounds compared to the initial oil, this positive effect being particularly marked in the case of MCM-36 (28.3 wt% in yield, which corresponds to 38.9 wt% in concentration, in comparison with 43.5 wt% of the raw oil).

Regarding aliphatic compounds, the paraffin (PAR) content consistently decreased across all catalysts compared to the initial pyrolysis oil (35.6 wt%), dropping below 30 wt% in every case. This fact evidences that paraffins readily undergo cracking and dehydrogenation reactions

when exposed to the acid sites of the zeolites, in line with the mechanism of protolytic cracking of alkanes using different zeolites reported by Kotrel et al. [39]. Interestingly, while paraffin content decreases universally, the olefin (OL) content increases notably in the case of TNU-9, reaching 12 wt%, the highest among the tested catalysts. This behaviour suggests that, although TNU-9 possesses a moderate Brønsted acid site concentration (0.34 mmol·g⁻¹), its lack of accessible Brønsted acidity (confirmed by FTIR-DTBPY) and its weak acid strength (3 % of Brønsted acid sites remains at 450 °C) limit the further transformation of relatively long-chain olefins, which accumulate in the product stream rather than progressing through secondary reactions like cracking, cyclization or aromatization.

All zeolites improved the mono-aromatic hydrocarbons (MAH) content relative to the initial oil (5.5 wt%), with MWW-type zeolites performing particularly well. Among them, MCM-36 achieved the highest MAH yield (11 wt%), followed by MCM-56 (9.3 wt%), MCM-49 (9 wt%), and MCM-22 (8.4 wt%). MCM-36 benefits from a very high external surface area and mesopore volume, which enhance molecular transport, as well as its high concentration of externally accessible Brønsted acid sites (0.15 mmol·g⁻¹, FTIR-DTBPY). This accessibility promotes efficient dehydrogenation, cyclisation and aromatisation reactions, favouring the selective production of monoaromatics from paraffinic and olefinic species, as it has been previously reported [40].

With respect to naphthenes (NAPH), their content increased for all zeolites except MCM-36, which exhibited the lowest NAPH yield. This is consistent with MCM-36's strong aromatisation capacity, driven by its high external surface area and abundant accessible Brønsted sites, which promote the conversion of saturated ring structures into aromatic compounds. In contrast, zeolites like MCM-56, which also show enhanced surface accessibility, facilitate partial ring closure and hydrogenation, favouring the formation of naphthenes.

On the other hand, the production of other aromatic families such as poly-aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and indanes (IND) was negligible for all catalysts, indicating that the selected conditions and catalysts favour selective monoaromatic generation without significant formation of heavier aromatics.

3.4. Zeolite performance in the dehalogenation of waste plastics pyrolysis oil

To assess the impact of different zeolites on the dehalogenation efficiency of the initial oil, Figure 7A displays the average chlorine content in the oil phase over the 4-h reaction tests at a WHSV of 5h⁻¹, while Figure 7B shows the chlorine distribution between the solid (coke deposited over the catalyst) and liquid (oil) phases. As observed in Figure 7A, MWW-type zeolites — particularly MCM-36 and MCM-56 — demonstrate the most effective dehalogenation, reducing the chlorine concentration in the oil to approximately 42 ppm, compared to 290 ppm in the untreated feedstock. MCM-49 also performs similarly (43 ppm), while MCM-22 shows a slightly higher value of 52.5 ppm, indicating a consistent and efficient behaviour across all MWW materials. Thus, these values fall at or below the commonly cited 50 ppm threshold [7], considered acceptable for further refining of waste plastics pyrolysis oil. Therefore, the performance of these MWW-type zeolites aligns well with practical industrial requirements for pyrolytic oil upgrading. In contrast, TNU-9, which presents limited accessibility to the pore network and almost no external Brønsted acidity, exhibits a significantly lower dehalogenation degree, resulting in an oil with a chlorine content of 106 ppm. It can also be seen that in the absence of a catalyst (blank experiment), chlorine cannot be removed from the oil, showing the same concentration as in the initial feedstock (290 ppm).

The extent of chlorine retention correlates closely with the structural and acidic properties of the zeolites. As shown in Figure 7B, MWW zeolites retain more than 80 wt% of the chlorine in the solid/coke phase, whereas TNU-9 retains only around 65 wt%. In this way, it can be envisaged that their high content of external Brønsted acid

Fig. 6. Overall yield of hydrocarbon families quantified by GC-MS obtained in the plastic pyrolysis oil upgrading using different zeolites ($T = 450\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, WHSV = 5 h⁻¹, $t = 0 - 4$ h). Note: PAR = Paraffin; OL = Olefin; MAH = Monoaromatic hydrocarbons; NAPH = Naphthenes; PAH = Polyaromatic hydrocarbons; IND = Indanes and Indenes).

Fig. 7. (A and C) Oil Cl content and (B and D) chlorine distribution in the different fractions of the plastic pyrolysis oil upgrading using different zeolites ($T = 450\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\text{WHSV} = 5$ and 10 h^{-1} , $t = 0 - 4$ h).

sites—especially in MCM-36 and MCM-56—enhances the interaction with C–Cl bonds in large components promoting a more effective oil dehalogenation. This structure–function relationship is further underscored by the observation that chlorine species are predominantly immobilised in the solid/coke phase. Importantly, almost no halogenated compounds—neither HCl nor organochlorides species—were detected in the gas stream (Cl balance was close to 100 %), indicating that these materials prevent the release of volatile halogen species. This is a key advantage as it eliminates the need for downstream Cl capture or neutralisation units in the gas processing line.

Comparing with literature data, a clearer picture emerges of the advantages offered by zeolite-based strategies. Park et al. [41] demonstrated that $\text{WO}_x/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ catalysts deliver superior dehalogenation performance, reducing halogen content in pyrolysis oil derived from household vinyl waste from 428 to 17 ppm (96 %), significantly outperforming our zeolite system. However, their activity is largely restricted to chlorine and wax removal, with a little improvement in oil quality. Similarly, Ni-loaded ZSM-5 has also been tested with a real plastic pyrolysis oil as feedstock, displaying a dual function as it operates as a solid acid to facilitate the removal of covalently bound chlorine and as an adsorbent for ionic chlorine species via interaction with the metal sites. This dual role underlines the versatility of metal–zeolite systems in addressing halogen contaminants, although the overall extent of dechlorination remained limited (from 900 to 513 ppm, 43 %) [42].

In the present work, the tested zeolite catalysts not only ensure chlorine removal within industrial specifications but also drive a profound transformation of the oil, effectively decreasing heavy fractions

and selectively enriching it in monoaromatic compounds of high petrochemical value—an outcome not achieved in the aforementioned studies. Moreover, these zeolite catalysts promote the formation of olefin-rich gases, which are also interesting components as raw chemicals.

However, under the relatively mild space velocity conditions used in the above tests (5 h^{-1}), the differences in performance among the MWW materials are not very pronounced, showing they behave similarly in terms of dechlorination. This lack of clear differentiation among MWW-type catalysts at low WHSV prompted further investigation under more demanding conditions ($\text{WHSV} = 10\text{ h}^{-1}$) in order to evaluate their relative activity and stability when operating under limited contact time and reduced catalyst availability. Under this regime, the differences among catalysts become more pronounced. Figure 7C shows the overall oil chlorine concentration obtained along the 4 h duration tests. These results highlight that MCM-36 and MCM-56 maintain a high dechlorination performance, achieving final chlorine levels of 46.9 and 53.5 ppm, respectively, just slightly superior to those obtained at $\text{WHSV} = 5\text{ h}^{-1}$. Conversely, MCM-49 and MCM-22 exhibit significantly higher oil chlorine contents (130.7 and 81.7 ppm, respectively) than in the previous tests, indicating a pronounced drop in dehalogenation efficiency as the catalyst loading is reduced. TNU-9 again shows the poorest performance, with chlorine content in the oil reaching 144 ppm.

The chlorine distribution between the solid and liquid phases (Figure 7D) confirms these trends. MCM-36 and MCM-56 still retain over 80 wt% of the chlorine in the solid phase even at high WHSV, indicating good dechlorination capability. In contrast, MCM-22 and MCM-49 fall to

around 72–55 wt%, and TNU-9 drops below 50 wt%, underscoring its limited dechlorination capacity when using a lower catalyst amount.

In addition to the average dechlorination performance, it is also insightful to examine the time evolution of chlorine concentration in the oil for each zeolite under the two tested WHSV conditions, as presented in Figure 8. Overall, all zeolitic materials exhibit signs of deactivation throughout the reaction, as evidenced by the gradual increase in the chlorine concentration in the oil phase, indicating a progressive decline in dehalogenation efficiency. However, the extent and pattern of deactivation differ significantly depending on the zeolite structure and the applied WHSV.

For TNU-9, the most notable difference between 5 and 10 h⁻¹ occurs during the first hour, denoting that its initial dechlorination capacity is quickly exhausted. MCM-22 and MCM-49 display a progressive decay in the dechlorination degree that, for the second sample, is accelerated when working at WHSV = 10 h⁻¹. This fact denotes that the dechlorination capability of MCM-49 is very sensitive to catalyst loading, probably due to the low content of external Brønsted acid sites, which become rapidly covered by the coke deposits. MCM-56 exhibits a high dechlorination capacity, although with a marked increase in oil chlorine concentration between 2.5 and 3.5 h, particularly under 5 h⁻¹ WHSV. Notably, MCM-36 shows the most stable behaviour, with just a moderate

increase in the oil chlorine content over time, pointing to a lower degree of deactivation and higher robustness of the active sites responsible for dechlorination, irrespective of the space velocity. This behaviour reflects not only the inherent textural and acidic robustness of this material, but also its potential suitability for continuous or semi-continuous industrial dechlorination processes, where prolonged catalyst life and consistent product quality are critical.

3.5. Regeneration ability of MCM-36 zeolite

Given that MCM-36 exhibited the most promising performance among the zeolitic catalysts tested in the upgrading of plastic pyrolysis oils, particular attention was devoted to evaluating its regeneration behaviour. Assessing the capacity of the material to recover its catalytic activity after use is essential to determine its long-term applicability and economic feasibility. Therefore, an additional experiment was carried out at 10 h⁻¹ in order to verify whether MCM-36 can retain its activity, selectivity, and dehalogenation capacity after the regeneration. A two-step procedure was applied for the catalyst regeneration. Firstly, the spent catalyst was subjected to Soxhlet extraction with tetrahydrofuran, which afforded the removal of all the halogenated species. In a second step, the remaining Cl-free carbonaceous matter was removed by air

Fig. 8. Evolution along the time on stream of the Cl content in the plastic pyrolysis oil after zeolite upgrading ($T = 450\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\text{WHSV} = 5$ and 10 h^{-1}) in comparison with that of the raw oil (constant grey line).

calcination, thus avoiding the possible formation of hazardous/toxic species that could occur by direct combustion of the spent catalyst.

As shown in Figure 9A, the regenerated MCM-36 catalyst exhibits product distributions that closely resemble those obtained with the fresh material. The overall yields of the main fractions (oil, gas, and coke) remain essentially unchanged, with only a minor increase in liquid yield and the corresponding decrease in the production of gaseous hydrocarbons. In the gaseous fraction, the regenerated sample preserves the ability to generate light olefins, particularly C₃ and C₄ hydrocarbons, although with a slight reduction compared to the fresh catalyst (Figure 9B). In the liquid phase, the distribution of hydrocarbon families quantified by GC-MS shows only very small differences between the fresh and regenerated catalyst. A slight increase in paraffins is observed (from 23.2 to 27.2 wt% for the fresh and regenerated materials, respectively), while the remaining families exhibit only minor reductions (Figure 9C). Importantly, the yield of heavy components is essentially the same in both experiments (Figure 9A). Finally, the dehalogenation degree is maintained at high values after regeneration (Figure 9D), ensuring efficient removal of chlorine-containing compounds from the pyrolysis oil.

These results indicate that MCM-36 preserves most of its catalytic properties after regeneration, with only minor differences in activity and selectivity. Therefore, the material can be considered regenerable as its performance for upgrading the plastic pyrolysis oils is almost completely recovered by the two-step regeneration treatment here applied.

4. Conclusions

A series of TUN and MWW zeolite samples (TNU-9, MCM-22, MCM-49, MCM-56 and MCM-36) have been synthesised with high

crystallinity. These materials, although having some structural similarities, present important differences in terms of textural and acidic properties, as well as regarding their accessibility when processing large molecules.

The feedstock employed here is an oil generated at an industrial scale by pyrolysis of real waste plastics, which can be considered representative of the liquid fraction obtained in this type of treatment. These treatments are currently of high relevance due to the problematic and environmental impacts associated with waste plastics. The use of real pyrolysis oil in this work is of high practical value compared to most previous literature, which mainly deals with model mixtures. However, it imposes significant challenges due to the complex composition of this feedstock, characterised by a high content of bulky components and a significant Cl content.

All tested zeolitic materials showed activity for the oil upgrading, shifting its composition to hydrocarbons with higher value for the formulation of both transportation fuels and raw chemicals, although with clearly different extents. Overall, a direct relationship was observed between the catalytic activity in reactions producing light olefins or naphthenic/aromatic hydrocarbons, and the zeolite accessibility regarding external acid sites and external surface area. This fact was also observed in terms of the oil dechlorination degree achieved in each case. The best performance for the oil upgrading and dechlorination, as well as regarding the production of light olefins by cracking, was attained with zeolites MCM-56 and MCM-36, being assigned to their remarkable accessibility. In particular, the behaviour of MCM-36 was very interesting as it demonstrated the highest gaseous olefins and aromatic hydrocarbons production, together with a high degree of oil dechlorination that declined slowly along the time on stream. Also, this material could be efficiently regenerated by a sequential combination of

Fig. 9. Comparison of the performance of the fresh and regenerated MCM-36 catalyst for the upgrading of the waste plastics pyrolysis ($T = 450\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\text{WHSV} = 5\text{ h}^{-1}$): (A) yields of the product fractions (oil, gas and coke), (B) yields of the individual hydrocarbons identified in the gaseous fraction, (C) yield of hydrocarbon families in the oil fraction and (D) dehalogenation degree of the oil phase. Note: In panel (A), the hatched portion of the oil yield corresponds to the heavy components not detected by GC-MS.

Soxhlet extraction and air calcination procedures, recovering most of the initial performance, which allowed both Cl and carbonaceous matter to be removed in a safe way.

The THF treatment of the spent catalysts indicated that most of the Cl removed from the oil was trapped by the zeolite. Therefore, it can be concluded that the oil upgrading process through a combination of catalytic and adsorption events.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jiří Čejka: Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Pavla Eliášová:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Patricia Pizarro:** Validation, Formal analysis. **David P. Serrano:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Martin Kubů:** Methodology, Formal analysis. **Jennifer Cueto:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Alberto Pinto:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Lidia Amodio:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This work is part of the action PCI2023–143433, funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by the European Union. The authors also acknowledge the EIG-Concert Japan Program (Nr. 8123003). J.C. acknowledges the project TECHSCALE (No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004587) for using JEOL JSM-IT800 microscope and the Charles University Centre of Advanced Materials (CUCAM– OP VVV Excellent Research Teams, no. CZ.02.1.01/0.0/0.0/15_003/0000417) for providing infrastructure enabling this research. The authors thank Subhajyoti Samanta, Ph.D. for FTIR measurements, Assoc. Prof. M. Shamzhy for the discussion of the FTIR spectroscopy results and Mgr. Monika Remzová, Ph.D. for SEM analysis. The authors acknowledge the Viničná Microscopy Core Facility (VMCF of the Faculty of Science, Charles University), a facility supported by MEYS CR (LM2023050 Czech-BioImaging), for their support and assistance with this work.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.cattod.2025.115594](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2025.115594).

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- R. Miandad, M.A. Barakat, A.S. Aburiazza, M. Rehan, I.M.I. Ismail, A.S. Nizami, Effect of plastic waste types on pyrolysis liquid oil, *Int. Biodeterior. Biodegrad.* 119 (2017) 239–252, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibiod.2016.09.017>.
- B. Debnath, R. Chowdhury, S.K. Ghosh, Sustainability of metal recovery from E-waste, *Front. Environ. Sci. Eng.* 12 (2018), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11783-018-1044-9>.
- T.S. Muzata, L.M. Matuana, M. Rabnawaz, Challenges in the mechanical recycling and upcycling of mixed postconsumer recovered plastics (PCR): a review, *Curr. Res. Green. Sustain. Chem.* 8 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crgsc.2024.100407>.
- P. Das, J.C.P. Gabriel, C.Y. Tay, J.M. Lee, Value-added products from thermochemical treatments of contaminated e-waste plastics, *Chemosphere* 269 (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2020.129409>.
- R. Miandad, M.A. Barakat, A.S. Aburiazza, M. Rehan, A.S. Nizami, Catalytic pyrolysis of plastic waste: a review, *Process Saf. Environ. Prot.* 102 (2016) 822–838, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psep.2016.06.022>.
- A. Lopez-Urionabarrenechea, I. De Marco, B.M. Caballero, M.F. Laresgoiti, A. Adrados, Upgrading of chlorinated oils coming from pyrolysis of plastic waste, *Fuel Process. Technol.* 137 (2015) 229–239, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuproc.2015.04.015>.
- J. Gutzeit, Effect of Organic Chloride Contamination of Crude Oil on Refinery Corrosion, in: *Corrosion 2000*, Orlando (Florida), 2000.
- A. Lopez-Urionabarrenechea, I. de Marco, B.M. Caballero, A. Adrados, M. F. Laresgoiti, Empiric model for the prediction of packaging waste pyrolysis yields, *Appl. Energy* 98 (2012) 524–532, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2012.04.021>.
- S. Kumagai, K. Fujiwara, T. Nishiyama, Y. Saito, T. Yoshioka, Chemical feedstock recovery through plastic pyrolysis: challenges and perspectives toward a circular economy, *ChemSusChem* (2025), <https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.202500210>.
- S. Bellessai, A. Azara, N. Abatzoglou, Recent advances in the decontamination and upgrading of waste plastic pyrolysis products: an overview, *Processes* 10 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr10040733>.
- C. Cao, W. Xuan, S. Yan, Q. Wang, Zeolites synthesized from industrial and agricultural solid waste and their applications: a review, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 11 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2023.110898>.
- A. Marino, A. Aloise, H. Hernando, J. Ferosmo, D. Cozza, E. Giglio, M. Migliori, P. Pizarro, G. Giordano, D.P. Serrano, ZSM-5 zeolites performance assessment in catalytic pyrolysis of PVC-containing real WEEE plastic wastes, *Catal. Today* 390391 (2022) 210–220, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2021.11.033>.
- J.L. Toro-Trochez, D.A. De Haro Del Río, L. Sandoval-Rangel, E. Bustos-Martínez, F. J. García-Mateos, R. J. Ruiz-Rosas, T. Rodríguez-Mirasol, E.S. Cordero, Carriolo-Pedraza, catalytic fast pyrolysis of soybean hulls: focus on the products, *J. Anal. Appl. Pyrolysis* 163 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaap.2022.105492>.
- J. Cueto, G. Pérez-Martin, L. Amodio, M. Paniagua, G. Morales, J.A. Melero, D. P. Serrano, Upgrading of solid recovered fuel (SRF) by dechlorination and catalytic pyrolysis over nanocrystalline ZSM-5 zeolite, *Chemosphere* 339 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2023.139784>.
- J. López, L. Amodio, M. del Mar Alonso-Doncel, J. Cueto, H. Hernando, M. Mazur, J. Čejka, P. Pizarro, D.P. Serrano, Enhanced oil dehalogenation during catalytic pyrolysis of WEEE-derived plastics over Fe- and Ca-modified zeolites, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 12 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2023.111790>.
- K.H. Lee, Effects of the types of zeolites on catalytic upgrading of pyrolysis wax oil, *J. Anal. Appl. Pyrolysis* 94 (2012) 209–214, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaap.2011.12.015>.
- S. Wang, H. Kim, D. Lee, Y.R. Lee, Y. Won, B.W. Hwang, H. Nam, H.J. Ryu, K. H. Lee, Drop-in fuel production with plastic waste pyrolysis oil over catalytic separation, *Fuel* 305 (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2021.121440>.
- O. Rogala, K.A. Tarach, L. Lakiss, A. Kordek, V. Valtchev, J.P. Gilson, K. Góra-Marek, Shaped zeolites y for polypropylene cracking, *Appl. Catal. B Environ.* 365 (2025), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2024.124893>.
- J. López, L. Amodio, M. del Mar Alonso-Doncel, J. Cueto, H. Hernando, M. Mazur, J. Čejka, P. Pizarro, D.P. Serrano, Enhanced oil dehalogenation during catalytic pyrolysis of WEEE-derived plastics over Fe- and Ca-modified zeolites, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 12 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2023.111790>.
- P.Y. Dapsens, C. Mondelli, J. Pérez-Ramírez, Design of Lewis-acid centres in zeolitic matrices for the conversion of renewables, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 44 (2015) 7025–7043, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c5cs00028a>.
- W.J. Roth, P. Nachtigall, R.E. Morris, J. Čejka, Two-dimensional zeolites: current status and perspectives, *Chem. Rev.* 114 (2014) 4807–4837, <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr400600f>.
- W.J. Roth, D.L. Dorset, G.J. Kennedy, Discovery of new MWW family zeolite EMM-10: identification of EMM-10P as the missing MWW precursor with disordered layers, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 142 (2011) 168–177, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2010.10.052>.
- J. Kennedy, S.L. Lawton, Sorbate-induced changes in the ²⁹Si MAS NMR spectrum of highly siliceous MCM-22, *Paulsboro*, 1996. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0927-6513\(96\)00069-7](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0927-6513(96)00069-7).
- F. Gramm, C. Baerlocher, L.B. McCusker, S.J. Warrander, P.A. Wright, B. Han, S. B. Hong, Z. Liu, T. Ohsuna, O. Terasaki, Complex zeolite structure solved by combining powder diffraction and electron microscopy, *Nature* 444 (2006) 79–81, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature05200>.
- M. Kubů, S.I. Zones, J. Čejka, TUNTUN, IMF and-SVR zeolites; synthesis, properties and acidity, *Top. Catal.* (2010) 1330–1339, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11244-010-9591-8>.
- A. Korzeniowska, J. Grzybek, K. Kalahurska, M. Kubu, W.J. Roth, B. Gil, The structure-catalytic activity relationship for the transient layered zeolite MCM-56 with MWW topology, *Catal. Today* 345 (2020) 116–124, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2019.09.044>.
- V. Zholobenko, C. Freitas, M. Jendrlin, P. Bazin, A. Travert, F. Thibault-Starzyk, Probing the acid sites of zeolites with pyridine: quantitative AGIR measurements of the molar absorption coefficients, *J. Catal.* 385 (2020) 52–60, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcat.2020.03.003>.
- C.A. Emeis, Determination of integrated molar extinction coefficients for infrared absorption bands of pyridine adsorbed on solid acid catalysts, *J. Catal.* (1993) 347–354, <https://doi.org/10.1006/jcat.1993.1145>.

- [29] M. Shamzhy, B. Gil, M. Opanasenko, W.J. Roth, J. Čejka, MWW and MFI frameworks as model layered zeolites: structures, transformations, properties, and activity, *ACS Catal.* 11 (2021) 2366–2396, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscatal.0c05332>.
- [30] A. Corma, V. Fornés, F. Fornés, L. Forni, F. Márquez, J. Martínez-Triguero, D. Moscotti, 2,6-Di-Tert-Butyl-Pyridine as a probe molecule to measure external acidity of zeolites, *J. Catal.* (1998) 451–458, <https://doi.org/10.1006/jcat.1998.2233>.
- [31] L. Lakiss, A. Vicente, J.P. Gilson, V. Valtchev, S. Mintova, A. Vimont, R. Bedard, S. Abdo, J. Bricker, Probing the Brønsted acidity of the external surface of Faujasite-Type zeolites, *ChemPhysChem* 21 (2020) 1873–1881, <https://doi.org/10.1002/cphc.202000062>.
- [32] M. Pagano, H. Hernando, J. Cueto, P.L. Cruz, J. Dufour, I. Moreno, D.P. Serrano, Insights on the acetic acid pretreatment of wheat straw: changes induced in the biomass properties and benefits for the bio-oil production by pyrolysis, *Chem. Eng. J.* 454 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2022.140206>.
- [33] A. Lago, H. Hernando, J.M. Moreno, D.P. Serrano, J. Feroso, Valorisation of a lignin-rich residue via catalytic pyrolysis over ZrO₂/ZSM-5 technical catalyst, *Fuel Process. Technol.* 215 (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuproc.2021.106746>.
- [34] M. Thommes, K. Kaneko, A.V. Neimark, J.P. Olivier, F. Rodriguez-Reinoso, J. Rouquerol, K.S.W. Sing, Physisorption of gases, with special reference to the evaluation of surface area and pore size distribution (IUPAC Technical Report), *Pure Appl. Chem.* 87 (2015) 1051–1069, <https://doi.org/10.1515/pac-2014-1117>.
- [35] S. Maheshwari, C. Martínez, M. Teresa Portilla, F.J. Llopis, A. Corma, M. Tsapatsis, Influence of layer structure preservation on the catalytic properties of the pillared zeolite MCM-36, *J. Catal.* 272 (2010) 298–308, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcat.2010.04.011>.
- [36] P. Gao, Z. Hu, Y. Sheng, W. Pan, L. Ding, L. Tang, X. Chen, F. Wang, Pyrolysis of municipal plastic waste: chlorine distribution and formation of organic chlorinated compounds, *Sci. Total Environ.* 912 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.169572>.
- [37] F. Bleken, W. Skistad, K. Barbera, M. Kustova, S. Bordiga, P. Beato, K.P. Lillerud, S. Svelle, U. Olsbye, Conversion of methanol over 10-ring zeolites with differing volumes at channel intersections: comparison of TNU-9, IM-5, ZSM-11 and ZSM-5, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 13 (2011) 2539–2549, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c0cp01982h>.
- [38] K.A. Tarach, G. Jajko, M. Palomino, F. Rey, K. Góra-Marek, Constrained and open mesoporosity in polypropylene cracking: insight from spectroscopic investigations of acidity, diffusion, and activity, *Langmuir* 40 (2024) 6918–6932, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.langmuir.3c03880>.
- [39] S. Kotel, H. Knözinger, B.C. Gates, The Haag–Dessau mechanism of protolytic cracking of alkanes, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 3536 (2000) 11–20, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1387-1811\(99\)00204-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1387-1811(99)00204-8).
- [40] W. Lee, T. Lee, H.G. Jang, S.J. Cho, J. Choi, K.S. Ha, Effects of hierarchical zeolites on aromatization of acetylene, *Catal. Today* 303 (2018) 177–184, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2017.09.014>.
- [41] S.J. Park, S.H. Kang, J.G. Hwang, H.S. Kim, J. Seok, M. Choi, Y.H. Choi, J.W. Lee, Upgrading of actual pyrolysis oil derived from waste plastics through catalytic cracking of chlorinated heavy fractions using alumina-supported tungsten oxide, *Mol. Catal.* 572 (2025), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mcat.2024.114755>.
- [42] W. Jeon, S.-A. Choi, Y.-D. Kim, K.-H. Lee, Low-temperature dechlorination methods for pyrolysis oil of municipal plastic waste, *Fuel* 381 (2025), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2024.133286>.